

28 **Abstract**

29 In this work the relationship between *Schistosoma mansoni* (Sm) and the induction and
30 progression of colorectal cancer (CRC) is examined. Various clinical studies reviewed here
31 yield inconsistent results, with some reporting no association between Sm infection and CRC
32 and others suggesting a probable to strong association. Here we propose a number of plausible
33 mechanisms whereby Sm infection might contribute to CRC induction and/or progression.
34 These factors are (1) chronic inflammation, (2) exposure to parasite linked antigens and
35 genotoxic products, especially soluble egg antigens (SEAs) and (3) alteration of the intestinal
36 microbiota. These factors probably predispose humans towards CRC and can help in CRC
37 progression however only widespread epidemiological, clinical and pathological studies can
38 firmly establish their role or a complete lack of it.

39 **Keywords:** *Schistosoma mansoni*, colorectal cancer, carcinogenesis, inflammation, soluble
40 egg antigens, ROS.

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56 **Introduction**

57 Cancer involves adverse changes in regular cellular behaviour which prompts cells to divide
58 continuously and this interferes with the normal physiology of the body (Cooper & Hausman
59 2007; Jain et al., 2019). Cancer induction is mostly attributed to undesirable expression of
60 proteins coded by proto-oncogenes or/and tumour suppressor genes, stimulated by mutations
61 at the genetic level. A ‘loss-of-function’ mutation in tumour suppressor genes such as *p53*,
62 *PTEN*, *APC* and/or a ‘gain-of-function’ mutation in proto-oncogenes like *Her-2/Neu*, *c-myc*,
63 *Kras*, *VEGF* leads to carcinogenesis (Lodish et al 2003; Jain & Kumar, 2020).

64 The International Agency for Research on Cancer (IARC) categorizes human carcinogens into
65 different groups depending upon the supporting evidence for their cancer inducing potential.
66 Agents in group 1 are positive for human carcinogenicity whereas those in group 2 are plausible
67 carcinogens, lacking conclusive evidence of their cancer inducing abilities in humans. Group
68 2 is sub-divided as follows - 2A (probable carcinogens) and 2B (possible carcinogens). For
69 agents in group 3 there exists a lack of any carcinogenicity proof in humans but there is
70 sufficient evidence of cancer in animal models along with strong mechanistic evidences which
71 are not operating in humans (IARC website; Jain & Rana, 2024).

72 An array of trematodes which belong to three genera - namely *Schistosoma*, *Clonorchis* and
73 *Opisthorchis*, have been classified in different carcinogen groups by IARC (Jain et al., 2023).
74 Schistosomes or blood flukes, are mostly parasitic to warm-blooded vertebrates and cause
75 schistosomiasis (Roberts et al., 2012), a disease whose pathogenesis is mostly dependent upon
76 deposited eggs and not the adult worms (Colley et al., 2014).

77 Colorectal Cancer (CRC) is the second most common cancer affecting women after breast
78 cancer (Sung et al., 2021). In males, it is the third most commonly diagnosed cancer after lung
79 and prostate cancers (Sung et al., 2021). In 2012, CRC was responsible for 8.5% of total cancer
80 mortality which increased to 9.4% in 2020 globally (Ferlay et al., 2015; Sung et al., 2021; Jain
81 et al., 2023). Based upon the site of onset, colon cancer accounts for about 49% of CRC cases,
82 rectal cancer accounts for 49.6% of cases whereas 1.25% of cases involve both sites combined
83 (Wang, 2019). Many studies have proposed a link between *Schistosoma mansoni* (Sm)
84 infection and CRC in humans and the IARC has placed CRC linked with Sm infection
85 (SMCRC) in group 3 (von Bülow et al., 2021).

86 This review has two major objectives. First, it presents various studies including
87 epidemiological, pathological, clinical, and case studies which point towards a probable
88 connection between Sm infection and CRC or a complete lack of it. Second, it enumerates
89 various mechanisms which are probably leading to CRC induction and are helping in its
90 progression.

91 **Sm infection and CRC: What the literature says**

92 One of the initial studies which looked into a possible link between Sm infection and CRC
93 focused on an 18-year-old girl, who was heavily infected with Sm and had a colloid
94 adenocarcinoma of the splenic flexure (Roman & Burke, 1926). The authors considered
95 schistosomiasis as the probable reason for the malignant tumour but they also pointed out that
96 colonic carcinoma did not occur with increased frequency in Sm endemic regions (Roman &
97 Burke, 1926). Another study pointed out the absence of causal relationship as they also argued
98 that though Sm has a non-uniform distribution throughout the globe but CRC occurs in the
99 continent of Africa with clear uniformity (Parkin et al., 1986).

100 In a study from Zaria, Nigeria which involved 8 patients below the age of twenty years, having
101 tumours in the recto-sigmoid region, one was found positive for Sm infection. However, no
102 causal or apparent link between Sm and CRC was analysed in the study (Ameh & Nmadu,
103 2000). A similar study which analysed surgical specimens of CRC patients in Nigeria over a
104 span of 10 years also reported schistosome infection in some CRC cases (Ojo et al., 1991).
105 Another case study reported the presence of cancer in the sigmoid colon along with Sm
106 infection (Salim et al., 2010). In Tanzania, a patient with intestinal obstruction and a
107 constrictive lesion at the sigmoid colon, was diagnosed with Sm egg deposition through
108 histological analysis and was positive for CRC (Herman et al., 2017).

109 In a recent case study from Nigeria, a 35-year old man infected with Sm, was suffering from
110 intestinal obstruction and had developed rectal cancer as well as a cirrhotic liver with hepatic
111 schistosomiasis. The authors advocated for extensive studies to determine if Sm is responsible
112 for CRC, as the number of cases with CRC and schistosomiasis are rising (Umoke et al., 2019).

113 A study from Riyadh, Saudi Arabia examined 216 colonic schistosomiasis patients concluded
114 that Sm infection usually doesn't predispose patients towards colorectal malignancy
115 (Mohamed et al., 1990). However, a different study from Saudi Arabia analysed two patients
116 for rectal cancer and reported that one of the patients who was suffering from rectum

117 adenocarcinoma, had extensive deposition of calcified Sm eggs and suggested that intestinal
118 schistosomiasis should be considered as pre-cancerous (Al-Mashat et al., 2001).

119 Another study involved an exhaustive analysis of 1199 patients. Of the total patients, 950
120 individuals had gastrointestinal diseases including schistosomiasis, amebiasis, candidiasis,
121 aspecific enterocolitis and intestinal tuberculosis among others, whereas 249 individuals had
122 no gastrointestinal diseases but other pathologies. In this study, 34 patients were identified with
123 tumours in the colorectal region and most of them additionally had either schistosomiasis or
124 amebiasis. It was concluded that chronic infection of gastrointestinal tract is associated with
125 colorectal cancer but the study did not suggest any biological mechanism behind such
126 transformations (Waku et al., 2005).

127 A ground-breaking study found that colitis associated with schistosome infection is linked with
128 an early onset of multi-centric CRC (i.e., a disorder with multiple CRC foci on the bowel
129 surface) with a high proportion of mucinous (mucus producing) carcinoma cells, as compared
130 to patients without SMCRC (Madbouly et al., 2007). Interestingly, tumors from patients with
131 Sm infection relative to those without the infection, had high *p53* gene (a tumour suppressor
132 gene) expression. Further, the patients in the SMCRC group were significantly younger as
133 compared to patients suffering with CRC not linked with Sm (34.52 ± 11.22 years vs. $50.73 \pm$
134 12.75 years, $p=0.02$). Hence, the chances of CRC being induced by Sm are more probable than
135 by other means like multiple mutations accumulating with time as advocated by multi-hit
136 model (Sutherland & Bailer, 1984). In the absence of Sm infection (and any other carcinogen),
137 multi-hit model advocates that multiple mutations would be required to induce CRC which
138 accumulate overtime and hence should involve older people (Sutherland & Bailer, 1984)

139 This overexpression of *p53* gene in SMCRC patients was the most interesting find of this study
140 (Madbouly et al., 2007), where the opposite was probably expected. The authors suspected that
141 Sm infection is solely responsible for the altered expression of *p53* protein, either by up-
142 regulating expression of *p53* gene by direct mutation in it or by inactivating/inhibiting *p53*
143 protein degradation. This altered activation of *p53* gene has been termed as the inciting event
144 behind CRC malignancy (**Fig.1**). Further, the inability of “excess” *p53* protein to suppress
145 tumour is explained through the possible inactivation of *p53* protein itself. This study calls for
146 more research into the role of pro-inflammatory cytokines like macrophage migration
147 inhibitory factor (MIF) which can inactivate *p53* protein during inflammation (Madbouly et al.
148 2007). While this study solely suspects schistosomal infection for altered *p53* protein

149 expression however no link either between adult worm or deposited eggs or their antigens and
150 altered *p53* gene expression has been proposed. Similarly, no pathway has been proposed in
151 this study on how this altered expression of p53 protein leads to CRC induction.

152 Altered expression of different genes has also been reported in another study from Egypt
153 involving 83 patients, where it was found that Sm probably played an important role in
154 dysregulation of apoptosis by altering the expression of Bcl-2 protein in CRC tissues. This
155 dysregulation may be dependent on hypothesized genotoxic products produced endogenously
156 throughout the course of Sm infection, as patients with CRC not linked with Sm didn't have
157 similar alterations of Bcl-2 protein expression (Zalata et al., 2005). An additional study found
158 Bcl-2 protein to be involved in migration and invasion of CRC cells *in-vitro* and advocated for
159 therapies based on targeting Bcl-2 protein (Koehler et al., 2013). Interestingly, Zalata's study
160 also analysed the expression patterns of *p53* and *c-Myc* genes and on the contrary to the above
161 mentioned study, it reported no differences in p53 (or c-Myc) expression patterns in CRC
162 patients with or without Sm infection (Zalata et al., 2005)

163 In another study from Sudan which involved a total of 93 patients, stool analysis documented
164 that out of these patients, 27 patients had Sm infection alone whereas 26 of them only had CRC
165 but no Sm infection. The remaining 40 patients were infected with Sm and had CRC. The study
166 found that patients with both CRC and Sm infection secreted clusterin and plasminogen
167 proteins which were not found in serum of CRC patients negative for Sm infection
168 (Abdelkareem et al., 2014). Studies have highlighted *de novo* synthesis of clusterin in CRC
169 cases (Andersen et al., 2007). This study argued that clusterin is involved in many processes
170 important for carcinogenesis (Fu et al., 2023) as well as metastasis (Peng et al., 2019) and its
171 expression in CRC patients positive for Sm infection points towards a probable link between
172 them. However, how worms or SEA can lead to this altered gene expression is not clear.

173 A study conducted in an endemic region of Brazil found that while the age of cancer diagnosis
174 and laterality (location of tumours) in CRC patients with or without Sm infection might be
175 similar, however, lymph node metastasis is increased in Sm positive patients (Almeida et al.,
176 2019). This study highlights a possible role of Sm infection in CRC progression irrespective of
177 its causal role. Another study reviewed the literature for evidences of a possible relationship
178 between Sm infection and CRC and reported important co-relations indicating a link between
179 them. The study also blamed the little attention being given to these endemic diseases behind
180 the ambiguity of their possible cancer inducing abilities (Abdalkareem & Yin, 2019).

181 **Possible mechanisms of Sm-induced carcinogenesis**

182 Though the links between Sm infection and CRC induction are relatively weak, however, many
183 studies have highlighted various mechanisms at cellular and genetic levels that could play roles
184 in carcinogenesis. Three prominent factors are highlighted: (1) chronic inflammation, (2)
185 exposure to parasite linked antigens and genotoxic products, especially soluble egg antigens
186 (SEAs) and (3) alteration of the intestinal microbiota.

187 **Chronic Inflammation**

188 Multiple studies have shown that intestinal schistosomiasis is linked with chronic inflammation
189 in response to deposited parasite eggs (Godyn et al., 2005; Nation et al. 2020). Though many
190 eggs penetrate the walls of blood vessels and eventually enter the lumen and are expelled from
191 the body with faeces, some eggs remain trapped in the intestinal tissue leading to pathology.
192 This local inflammation response can be massive (Schafer & Hale, 2001). Prolonged infection
193 leads to inflammatory polyposis, mucosal granularity, minute ulcers and haemorrhage
194 (Kołodziej et al., 2024). Chronic inflammation has been linked with the heightened production
195 of reactive oxygen species (ROS) (Mittal et al., 2014; Forrester et al., 2018; Chelombitko,
196 2019; Checa & Aran, 2020). Interestingly, schistosome antigens (particularly the ω -1
197 glycoprotein, a constituent of these antigens) are also linked with inflammasome activation
198 (Sanches et al., 2020).

199 ROS acts as a signalling molecule in low concentrations but at higher concentrations, it can act
200 as a cancer modulator (de Sá Junior et al., 2017). ROS can promote the conversion of normal
201 cells to malignant cells by promoting motility, genomic instability and oncogenic growth (Liou
202 & Storz, 2010; Singh & Manna, 2022). Chronic inflammation and ROS have been implicated
203 in cancer induction in the case of *S. haematobium* (Sh) infection and urinary bladder cancer
204 (UBC) and is also linked with *S. japonicum* infection and colorectal and liver cancer (Ishii et
205 al., 1989; Rosin, 1994; Jain et al., 2023; Jain & Rana, 2024; Jain, 2024a; Jain, 2024b). It is
206 likely that the deposited eggs of Sm lead to chronic inflammation and ROS generation which
207 could assist in colorectal carcinogenesis (**Fig.1**).

208 In a study, tumors from two patients with Sm infection displayed microsatellite instability
209 (MSI, an alteration in micro-satellite sequence number) and mutations in RAS family genes
210 that are important in controlling cell growth (Almeida et al. 2017). MSI is reported in multiple
211 cases of CRC (Boland & Goel, 2011; Nojadedh et al., 2018; Zeinalian et al., 2018) and RAS
212 mutations are linked with oncogenesis (Prior et al., 2012; Dinu et al., 2014; Zhu et al., 2021).

213 Note that ROS can cause chromosomal instability and MSI as it deactivates DNA repair
214 systems (Waris & Ahsan, 2006; Carini et al., 2017; Taieb et al., 2022) and hence possibly
215 leading to CRC induction.

216 **Soluble egg antigens (SEA)**

217 SEAs are derived from homogenized eggs of the parasite consisting of numerous proteins,
218 many of which are glycosylated (Mouser et al., 2019). SEAs from Sm can activate proto-
219 oncogene *c-Jun* (Weglage et al., 2020) which is known to crosstalk with Bcl-2 and enhance its
220 transcription (Li et al., 2003). As mentioned earlier, Bcl-2 has been reported to be upregulated
221 in some cases of SMCRC (Zalata et al., 2005). Such a link between SEAs and overexpression
222 of Bcl-2 might be behind the survival of CRC cells (**Fig.1**).

223 SEAs are not only responsible for interfering with expression patterns of proteins coded by
224 tumour suppressor genes and proto-oncogenes but they are extremely potent in promoting
225 angiogenesis, a crucial factor for cancer progression and metastasis (Costain et al., 2018). A
226 study showed that SEAs are capable of proliferating endothelial cells *in vitro* whereas adult Sm
227 worm extract exerted no such effect (Freedman & Ottesen, 1988). A following study (Loeffler
228 et al., 2002) showed that SEAs up-regulated endothelial cell vascular endothelial growth factor
229 (VEGF) which promoted angiogenesis and assists in metastasis (Marjon et al. 2004).

230 In other work it was shown that the extent of angiogenesis caused by SEA is influenced by the
231 genetic background of the host (Van de Vijver et al., 2006). Another study characterised and
232 partially purified an egg-derived factor which is pro-angiogenic in nature and can modulate
233 angiogenesis (Kanse et al., 2005). SEA has also been shown to stimulate liver macrophages to
234 produce hedgehog ligands which promoted alternative activation of macrophages and vascular
235 remodelling (Pereira et al., 2012) (**Fig.1**).

236 The role of SEA in activating *c-Jun* has already been stated above (Weglage et al., 2020). Being
237 a proto-oncogene, its activation leads to cellular proliferation. It not only plays a central role in
238 signal transduction (along with its above mentioned role with Bcl-2) but also inhibits the
239 expression of tumour suppressor genes and may promote angiogenesis as well (Shao et al.,
240 2021). Non-canonical WNT signalling pathway was also seen in epithelial colon cells exposed
241 to SEA (Weglage et al., 2020). WNT signalling is involved in an array of physiological
242 functions like apoptosis, proliferation and invasion and its dysregulation can contribute to
243 cancer induction (Zhang & Wang, 2020) (**Fig.1**). A role for c-Jun protein in carcinogenesis
244 further finds support from another study, where c-Jun protein's activation by SEAs is observed

245 in hamster and human hepatocytes and this may contribute to hepatocellular carcinogenesis
246 (Roderfeld et al., 2020).

247 While the work being done connecting the SEAs with probable CRC induction seems
248 promising, however, it should be noted that most of this work has been done *in vitro* and hence
249 its relevance should also be determined *in vivo*.

250 **Alteration of intestinal microbiota**

251 The alteration of the intestinal microbiome following Sm infection has been reported in many
252 *in-vivo* studies (Li et al. 2011; Jenkins et al. 2018; Chelakkot et al. 2018). Sm infection is
253 responsible for causing a shift in the global composition of the host's gut microbiota and these
254 changes indicate dysbiosis, which not only accompanies egg migration across intestinal walls
255 but also aids in granuloma formation (Schwartz & Fallon, 2018; Stark et al., 2023). However
256 adult male Sm worm have been reported to modulate host immunity and limit dysbiosis
257 (Floudas et al., 2019).

258 Sm infected mice have intense changes in their microbiota which coincided with the time of
259 egg production and involved expansion of bacterial populations from the *Lactobacillaceae*
260 family as well as the bacterium *Akkermansia muciniphila* (Jenkins et al. 2018). These bacterial
261 populations may favour chronic schistosome infection by enhancing the number of regulatory
262 cellular components or by repairing egg-induced damage to the intestinal wall (Chelakkot et
263 al. 2018). *Akkermansia muciniphila* has been identified as a biomarker for metabolic and
264 inflammatory disorders (Kathera & Vishwanath, 2021). Further, analysis of Sm infected mouse
265 urine and faeces at the metabolic level also revealed several changes in gut-bacteria related
266 metabolites (Li et al. 2011).

267 While all these changes in the intestinal microbiome are significant and could affect the
268 carcinogenic potential of Sm, however, a direct pathway linking these changes to CRC is not
269 clear and further work is needed.

270 **Discussion**

271 Various studies carried out to look for a link between Sm infection and CRC, generated mixed
272 outcomes where certain studies (Parkin et al., 1986) could not find any such connection
273 whereas others suggested a probable (Roman & Burke, 1926; Ojo et al., 1991; Umoke et al.,
274 2019) or strong (Al-Mashat et al., 2001; Waku et al., 2005; Madbouly et al., 2007) association.

275 While some recent studies have suggested a strong correlation, however, as often pointed out,
276 causation can never be attributed to correlations. A number of plausible mechanisms whereby
277 Sm infection might contribute to CRC induction and/or progression are outlined in **Fig. 1**.

278 High levels of clusterin in serum levels of CRC patients with Sm infection, relative to those
279 CRC patients negative for Sm infection, is one such evidence (Abdelkareem et al., 2014). The
280 role of clusterin in metastasis and its *de novo* synthesis in CRC cases has been reported
281 (Andersen et al., 2007; Peng et al., 2019), however the available literature is silent on how Sm
282 infection is leading to this over-expression. The pathway for the same needs to be decoded
283 which might involve an active role of SEAs (**Fig 1**). However, high levels of these proteins in
284 their serum can act as biomarkers for treatment of CRC patients with Sm infection.

285 Similarly, the involvement of WNT signalling pathways and transcription factors like c-Jun
286 points towards a higher probability of SEAs affecting normal cellular signalling, leading to
287 their transformation into malignant forms (Weglage et al, 2020). Not only c-Jun protein is
288 involved in pathways that directly affect proliferation, cellular survival and tissue
289 morphogenesis (Meng & Xia, 2011), but its role in active angiogenesis and inhibiting the
290 tumour suppressor genes is widely reported in literature (Shao et al., 2021). Zalata's study
291 further showed involvement of Bcl-2 protein (Zalata et al., 2005), and Bcl-2 is again known to
292 crosstalk with c-Jun protein and might help malignant cell to escape apoptosis and further
293 promote migration and invasion (Li et al., 2003; Koehler et al., 2013). SEAs are also known to
294 enhance angiogenesis (Costain et al., 2018) whereas the activation of non-canonical WNT
295 signalling pathway interferes with colon epithelial cell apoptosis and promote proliferation and
296 infiltration (Zhang & Wang, 2020). All of these factors together are potent enough to create
297 suitable environment for CRC induction which is best exemplified from hepatocellular
298 carcinoma induction by c-Jun's altered expression in human and hamster hepatocytes
299 (Roderfeld et al., 2020).

300 The most convincing pathway seems to be the generation of ROS through chronic
301 inflammation, which mutates an array of genes including proto-oncogenes and tumour
302 suppressor genes as well as inactivates DNA mismatch repair systems, leading to MSI and
303 inducing CRC (Liou & Storz, 2010; Singh & Manna, 2022). While ROS, along with other
304 factors, is known to induce cancers in association with other helminth species (e.g. Sh with
305 UBC; *Opisthorchis viverrini* and *Clonorchis sinensis* with cholangiocarcinoma (Jain & Rana,
306 2024)), the same needs to be demonstrated in case of Sm. Further, the factors generated or

307 activated in response to chronic inflammation and SEAs respectively, don't work in isolation
308 but in unison and appears to be complementing each other's action (**Fig.1**). The same is
309 demonstrated by SEAs ability to activate inflammasomes (Sanches et al., 2020).

310 The tissue being infected by the schistosomes also plays an important role in induction and
311 progression of cancer. Sh, which is in group 1 of IARC list and induces UBC, derives its cancer
312 induction potential partly from differential response of the bladder epithelial cells to Sh eggs
313 relative to response of epithelial cells of other tissues to Sm eggs (Nacif-Pimenta et al, 2019).

314 It can be hence concluded that Sm infection, particularly the chronic inflammation and
315 dysbiosis of gut microbiota, in response to deposited eggs and the SEAs, are either generating
316 entities like ROS, leading to mutations and chromosomal instability or affecting the expression
317 of crucial transcription factors and signal transducers, most of which are linked directly or
318 indirectly with carcinogenesis and hence suggest a probable role in CRC carcinogenesis. These
319 factors probably predispose humans towards CRC and can help in CRC progression (Madbouly
320 et al., 2007; Almeida et al., 2019; von Bülow et al., 2021)

321 However, this role is extremely weak and needs to be firmly established through widespread
322 epidemiological, clinical and pathological studies. The lack of causal cases of Sm infection and
323 CRC induction in humans justifies its positioning in group 3 of IARC classification and only
324 extensive studies in humans can either "promote" it to either of the two groups or establish a
325 complete lack of any such link.

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334 **Figure Legend**

335 **Figure 1:** Possible mechanism of colorectal cancer induction by *Schistosoma mansoni*
336 infection. Solid arrows shows established mechanisms whereas dotted arrows show possible
337 pathways. Factors linked with chronic inflammation are highlighted in yellow and those linked
338 with soluble egg antigens (SEA) are highlighted in green. Factors not clearly linked with either
339 but have an altered expression following schistosome infection are highlighted in blue. (ROS:
340 Reactive Oxygen species, MIF: Migration Inhibitory Factor, VEGF: Vascular Endothelial
341 Growth Factor, WNT: Wingless-Type MMTV integration site family)

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356 **Declarations**

357 Ethics Approval: Not applicable.

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361 Conflict Of Interest: None declared

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